

Design of a desk-size over-actuated PKM for lab earthquake simulations

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Abstract—This contribution presents the design process and the virtual testing of a lab equipment for earthquake simulations. The machine object of study is a redundantly actuated platform with parallel kinematics topology. As known, this kind of architecture owns extremely interesting features which make PKMs (Parallel Kinematics Machines) particularly feasible for recreating seismic events, in terms of displacements, accelerations and, consequently, inertial solicitations. Nonetheless, the use of a parallel over-actuated structure makes the design process challenging under many points of view: the mechanics, the sensorisation, and even the control of the shaking device must be tackled carefully from the design stage to come out with effective solutions.

Index Terms—shaking table, earthquake simulation, parallel kinematics machines, robot design

I. INTRODUCTION

To investigate how various structures and materials respond to seismic activity, it's essential to mimic the specific accelerations, velocities, and displacements typical of earthquakes. Parallel Kinematics Machines (PKMs) represent a widely used solution when is necessary to simulate a seismic event, despite their complex kinematic models, that vary from design to design, and their small workspace to machine volume ratio [1]; this type of machines provides significant advantages such as high stiffness and precision at elevated accelerations, crucial for designing vibrating systems.

Shaking table tests continue to be the most reliable and frequently utilized approach for validating the dynamics of structures, even after FEA (Finite Element Analysis) techniques development. Currently FEA models are only used to evaluate contexts that are challenging to replicate in the laboratory [2], or in which the effects of the earthquake are combined with other stresses such as thermal loads as in [3]. However, also in these scenarios, a laboratory test is always carried out to validate and tune the model and generally laboratory testing is always preferred to simulation, even if they present some difficulties and additional costs. A strong reduction in costs and simplification of all test equipment is achieved through a desktop vibrating machine: the strong reduction of the specimen mass and geometries allows to move from hydraulic actuator system to a totally electric one, ensuring a simpler and more manageable system. This, coupled with the benefits of operating on a smaller table,

facilitates the design of an affordable and user-friendly testing machine. The design process of a desktop shaking table is presented in this paper, starting from the base of the scaled problems: the similitude law.

Once the scaling factor and specifications for the actuators are determined, the kinematic arrangement needs to be established. Various options exist for designing a shaking platform, with the choice depending on the number of controlled axes. Table configurations with two actuators are possible, in these case the test machine is a little bit more complex but is possible to have two translational [4] or rotational DoF (Degree of Freedom) if an hooke joint is used [5]. To achieve 6 DoF, a minimum of six actuators are required [6]. It is possible to add actuators to have a better load distribution, keeping the 6 DoF, but the control and running cost of the machine will grow.

For the desktop machine a common scheme used for MAST was chosen, eight actuators for a 6 DoF platform. By using this configuration the machine results redundantly actuated, so control properly the table motion will be a very significant challenge. Despite opting for such a sophisticated scheme, the small size of the machine and the use of electric actuators allow to keep costs low.

Fig. 1. Joint topology of the desktop shaking table.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE DEVICE

To choose the right scale factor reference kinematic performances have been set, defining the accelerations and velocities, in terms of amplitude and frequency, that must be guaranteed in order to reproduce a seismic event. Furthermore, the aim is to design a table measuring approximately half a meter on each side intended for light and moderate scaled specimens, being able to use electric rather than hydraulic actuators. Following an in-depth research, a linear actuator meeting the desired kinematic performance criteria, capable of delivering adequate thrust and of compact dimensions was identified. The actuator is based on a stepper motor, so it is easy to control and not expensive. The use of this spec would result in a 400x400mm table, thus perfectly in line with the expected dimensions.

Eight linear actuators are used to move the platform: four of them are placed under the table in a vertical position, while the other four are mounted one for each side of the platform in a horizontally position. The horizontal and vertical actuators have different length but they share the same kinematics. All the actuators are connected to the ground by an universal joint and a spherical joint is used for platform connection. Considering that the actuator itself is equivalent to a prismatic joint, the shaking table can be represented in a schematic form as shown in the Figure 1.

Once the type of constraints has been defined, the mechanical design of the shaking table components can start. It is necessary to design special joints and components taking into account the dimensions of the table and its kinematics, but where possible, commercial parts were preferred to specifically designed parts in order to keep the manufacturing cost low.

The assembly phase of a parallel robot is certainly the most critical, during this phase maximum attention and accuracy are necessary to ensure that the geometries and real distances between the key points of the machine in space are the same as those envisaged by the project. The frame must guarantee the right position of the universal joints in space and at the same time must ensure robust fixing of the entire robot structure. It consists of five acrylic plates mounted together creating a cube without the upper surface. The robot will be placed inside this cube and the eight actuators will be mounted inserting their support plates into some appropriate slots present on the frame plates surfaces, useful as reference to respect the desired joint positions as shown in Figure 2.

The implementation and control of a redundantly actuated machine is not trivial, so it is required an efficient and accurate control strategy. This control architecture is based on actuators position feedback signals, thanks to which compliance with the imposed displacements is guaranteed: the actuation is regulated depending on the error obtained from the comparison of the desired displacement with the real one measured by the sensors. Furthermore effects of the external or internal disturbances are automatically compensated.

The laws of motion for each actuators are obtained through inverse kinematics: once the desired displacement of the platform has been established, it is possible to calculate the

Fig. 2. Final appearance of the desktop shaking table obtained via rendering of the CAD mode.

values of the lengths that the actuators must assume over time, so that the vibrating machine moves as planned.

III. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This contribution presents the design of a desktop shaking table. The aim is to obtain a machine with which it is possible to carry out tests on very miniaturized specimens, but still useful for research and experimentation purposes, avoiding the exorbitant costs associated with the management of large hydraulic systems required for one to one scale tests. Also the production cost of the table is limited, opting for less sophisticated manufacturing process while maintaining a more sophisticated kinematic scheme with a 6 DoF table.

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